

RESEARCH OF THE PLACE OF SOCIAL STRATA OF THE POPULATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FOOD CONSUMER MARKET IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The goal of any economic system is to meet the demand of the population for food, goods and services. To achieve this goal, modern scientific and technical achievements are used in production in the national economy, measures are taken related to the effective organization of labor and a clear division of labor. The delivery of products produced in the conditions of market economic relations to consumers in the form of finished products is carried out through the management of economic relations in the sphere of commodity circulation. A large number of small and medium-sized enterprises in the food industry do not have sufficient financial resources to use modern technologies, as well as to improve the level of professional training of employees. For this reason, the delivery of food products to the consumer in the form of the final product on the market is expensive for society, the total costs of all stages of turnover are approximately equal to half of the final price of the goods. . All this allows economists to come to the conclusion that the positive impact of increasing the technological level and organization of production on the efficient use of resources should be accelerated. To do this, it is necessary to look for new reserve opportunities to increase efficiency in the rationalization of relations between production and consumption. It is for this reason that it should be noted that the issue of managing economic relations in the food market and improving the forms of movement of goods to the market, as well as the development of the food market, has become an urgent issue.

Keywords: Economic System, Population, Enterprize, Consumer, Goods, Resources, Electronic Trade.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of any economic system is to ensure the demand of the population for food, goods and services. To achieve this goal, modern scientific and technical achievements are being introduced into production in the national economy, measures related to effective labor organization and accurate division of labor are being carried out. In the conditions of market economic relations, the supply of manufactured products to consumers in the form of a final product is realized through the management of economic relations in the sphere of trade turnover.

In the food sector, numerous small and medium-sized enterprises lack the financial means to introduce modern technologies, as well as to improve the level of professional training of employees. For this reason, the delivery of food to the consumer on the market in the form of the final product is expensive, the total costs of turnover at all stages are approximately equal to half of the final price of the goods.

All this allows economists to conclude that the growth of the technological level and the positive impact of the organization of production on the rational use of resources should accelerate. To do this, it is necessary to look for new reserve opportunities to increase efficiency in rationalizing the relationships between production and consumption. It is for this reason that it should be noted that the issue of managing economic relations and improving the forms of movement of goods to the market, as well as the development of the food market, has become relevant in the food market.

CRITICAL ANALYSIS

G. Simmel argues that money as the basis of rational calculations that take into account most of human behavior, a social institution coordinates this behavior and brings it to a common denominator. The type of money introduced by G. Simmel, which serves to rationalize social life, made it possible to explain the contradictory nature of socio-economic exchange and universal criteria. It also regulates people's behavior, makes it effective and shows that it acts as a measure of their value relations [1, 3]. The analysis of economic processes in modern societies based on behavior was developed on the basis of the structural and functional approach of T. Parsons and his student N. Smelzer [2]. They gave an institutional and socio-cultural interpretation of economic behavior as a subsystem of the social system. Merit of T. Parsons [3] consists in the fact that he developed an original system of institutional, socio-cultural, functional determination of rational economic behavior.

G. Becker investigated even more economic models of behavior [2, 5]. He used the greatest economic approach in analyzing the problems of family, education, and crime. G. Becker wrote that "the economic approach considers absolutized behavior in a broader range and obvious form than other approaches." Here we are talking about the function of profitability or maximizing the state. He showed that it doesn't matter-whether it's a family, a company, a trade union or government agencies, the mentioned check applies to all levels.

I. P. Chepurnoy developed his own consumer theory of reducing the profitability of goods in the food market with a decreasing line [8]. Representatives of the theory of the fall of the final profitability of a product by a descending line are trying to justify not only the theory of consumption, but also how the monetary incomes of consumers are distributed among various goods and services that they buy.

The Consumer Must Compromise

He must choose between alternative products in such a way that, in conditions of limited monetary resources, he can better meet his needs in terms of the choice of goods and services.

The author claims that the behavior of consumers in a particular free market is determined taking into account the ratio of real monetary incomes available to them for food components to the goods offered by the market.

G. S kitovsky managed to justify the presence of several sources of irrationality of consumers [5, 7].

In his opinion, firstly, here we are talking about a single example of spending funds, since any norm, even if it is developed by specialists, is inevitably unreasonable. Even if we establish an objective standard of consumption for each group of the population, depending on the size of the family and the size of income, we are unlikely to be able to justify the deviation of an individual consumer from the norm by any special demand or personal desire. But such exceptions indicate the irrationality of his behavior.

The second probable source of irrational consumer behavior may be a random instinct between instinct and pleasure. But instinctive behavior does not always cause a feeling of great satisfaction, if so, you need to go against all instincts for great pleasure. And for this, there must be internal order and discipline in solving everyday issues.

M. Holbrook focused on a broader topic, adhering to the basic principles of his previous research: “when a living organism acquires and uses certain products to achieve its goals and desires, all the limits of the value of the product potentially exist” [9]. In other words, the study of consumer behavior is extremely important for studying demand and its impact.

From the point of view of problem solving in marketing, there are three types of consumer behavior: behavior based on routine (old-fashioned, lazy, conservative) irritations, implying a limited and broad solution to the problem.

K. Horney gave the following classification of personalities: soft (obedient), aggressive (violent), independent [5]. At the same time, D. Risman [5, 6] and his colleagues distinguish three types of personality. At this time, he uses the concept of a social character: based on traditions, based on the behavior of other people, a self-confident person. Each of these types manifests itself in relationships and behavior. As for the public approach, it should be noted that at the end of the last century, the consumer problem began to develop very actively.

Goals and objectives of the study. The advanced organization of the relationship management system with food consumers in the national economy is the definition of forms. To achieve this goal, the following research tasks were set and consistently performed in the dissertation work:

- Studying the theory of consumption and determining its role in the development of national consumer markets;
- Development of methodological approaches to the management of food consumption markets.

The Results of the Study

The regulation of processes in society and the organization of effective management -which is served by the lack of effective laws, as well as the weakness of executive authorities in the implementation of adopted laws indicate a weakening of the influence of the system of state power. However, one issue should be particularly noted: the weakness of official state bodies does not mean that the ongoing processes are not controlled. In such cases, management passes to other structures, in fact, the implementation of the powers of the authorities is carried out according to unwritten laws and rules.

Economic analyses conducted by many scientists were associated with a comprehensive study of financial and economic processes, acting as a set of special methods and techniques, the interaction and conditioning of which among themselves occurs under the influence of various factors, and all this is reflected in a particular economic information system [3,6]. The author agrees with this consolidation of his economic analysis.

The organization of economic analysis of the activities of economic entities requires the implementation of three consecutive stages: preparatory, main, final. Let's clarify their content regarding the food market.

At the preparatory stage, the goals and objectives related to market analysis, the object and subject of research, as well as methods of analysis, information support, the main indicators of the system that allow us to characterize the consumer market as a trading format are determined.

The dynamics of changes in goods and services is reflected in the assortment index (JB) [4].

In most cases:

$$J_B = \frac{\sum B_1}{\sum B_0} \quad (1)$$

Where $\sum B_1$ и $\sum B_0$ – reporting and report on the base period.

It is possible to determine due to which factors changes in income occur.

It is based on the index construction rule, according to which, if a quantitative attribute changes, the qualitative indicators associated with it are also fixed in the base period. If qualitative indicators change, then quantitative indicators recorded during the reporting period act as a measurement criterion.

The total amount of income from the sale of services depends on the number of leased retail outlets (M_0 and M_1) and the volume of tariffs for a retail outlet (T_0 and T_1) [4, 6].

The sales revenue index is equal to:

$$J_B = \frac{\sum B_1 T_1}{\sum B_0 T_0} \quad (2)$$

Retail space index J_M – takes this form:

$$J_M = \frac{\sum M_1 T_0}{\sum M_0 T_0} \quad (3)$$

In the tariff index (which, like any index, reflects changes in the price factor), it is expressed as follows:

$$J_T = \frac{\sum T_1 M_1}{\sum T_0 M_1} \quad (4)$$

Overall revenue growth, as well as growth due to retail space and tariffs, are defined as differences in the calculations of the three indices.

Total income growth is equal to:

$$B = M_1 T_1 - M_0 T_0 \quad (5)$$

Increased revenue due to increased retail space:

$$B_M = M_1 T_0 - M_0 T_0 \quad (6)$$

Increased revenue due to increased tariffs:

$$B_T = T_1 M_1 - T_0 M_1 \quad (7)$$

Accordingly, the share of each (V) factor in the change in income is determined [4]:

$$V_M = \frac{\Delta B_M \times 100}{\Delta B}, \quad V_T = \frac{\Delta B_T \times 100}{\Delta B} \quad (8)$$

Calculations are carried out in the following areas:

1. The change in income under the simultaneous influence of both factors is equal to the total amount of changes in each of them:

$$\Delta_{MT} = \pm \Delta_M \pm \Delta_T \text{ v} \Delta M_1 T_1 - M_0 T_0 = (M_1 T_0 - M_0 T_0) + (M_1 T_1 - M_1 T_0) \quad (9)$$

2. The service sales index (JB) is equal to the product of the index of retail locations (JM) by the index of tariffs for retail locations (JT):

$$J_P = \frac{\sum p_\phi q_1}{\sum p_{\text{рыH}} q_1} \quad (10)$$

$\sum p_\phi q_1$ - The volume of trade in the conditions of lower prices on social days;

$\sum p_{\text{рыH}} q_1$ - Sales volume in terms of actual market prices.

The volume of turnover allows you to study the result of the activities of food markets. All this allows you to calculate how much the population earns on social days when prices are falling, and find its expression in the index:

$$\Delta p q_p = \sum p_\phi q_1 - \sum p_{\text{рыH}} q_1 \quad (11)$$

Another indicator characterizing public activity is the amount of costs incurred in the implementation of social programs: transportation of partially or completely free goods from private subsidiary farms, provision of retail space, equipment, additional retail space at discounted prices to local agricultural producers exporting their products from the garden and melons to the market for the purpose of sale.

But meeting the needs of market participants does not end with solving issues that are in the main interests. The market should offer a maximum of additional services as a modern trade format, create technical and technological conditions for market participants, organize fairs so that sellers sell their products at free market prices, and buyers receive high-quality, inexpensive products for personal consumption.

Based on the calculations, we were able to compile the following indicators for Azerbaijan (table 1.).

Calculations show that the social management of consumer demand is at a fairly acceptable level. But, as in all managerial situations, there are reserves for its improvement. It is aimed at balancing the interests of market participants in order to objectively assess the social activity of the food market and the formation of a management mechanism. Accordingly, there is a need to consider the significance of the estimated parameters for enterprises producing and supplying food, and consumers of these products.

Table 1: Results of Evaluation of the Integral Coefficient of Social Orientation of Consumer Market Management from the Position of an Entrepreneur

Indicators	Conditional expressions	Average indicators by respondents (%)
The coefficient of constancy of growth in sales of food products	Кп	80
Assessment of the organization of the market with sellers	Ко	35
Assessment of the level of sales of locally produced food products	Кпр	80
Productive assessment by entrepreneurs of their activities engaged in the sale of food products	Кр	90
Evaluation of social programs stimulating national consumer markets	Ксп	100
Integral indicators of social management of consumer demand	Кинт	72,5

Source: The table is compiled by the author based on the source [9].

A steadily developing economic entity should have permanent partners, therefore one of the key indicators for the food market is the number of sellers working in this format of trade for a long period of time. This criterion also affects the main criterion of the market volume - the income from the sale of services is expressed in the number of rented premises, characterizes the real interests of suppliers and manufacturers of consumer goods for the functioning of the market.

Thus, the presented indicators of economic analysis and a set of parameters that allow us to characterize the social orientation of markets can give an idea of their real situation as a modern trading format. At the same time, management activities are being developed to increase the competitiveness of the food market, continue its economic development in the future, and clarify the social vector in the functions of all market participants. The results of research on the study of the social orientation of food market management are reflected in the table below (table 2.).

Table 2: The Results of the Evaluation of the Integral Coefficient of the Social Orientation of Consumer Market Management from the Perspective of Consumers

Indicators	Conditional expressions	Average indicators by respondents (%)
Assessment of the level of sales of locally produced food products	Кпр	85
Evaluation of social programs stimulating national consumer markets	Ксп	100
Assessment of the diversity of the sold range of food products	Кша	70
Assessment of psychological comfort	Кпк	80
Integral indicators of social management of consumer demand	Кинт	83,0

Source: The table is compiled by the author based on the source [9].

A comparative analysis of actual consumption and recommended norms of food in the Republic of Azerbaijan shows that only 6 out of 10 basic foodstuffs are provided (bread, vegetables, meat, fish, sugar, vegetable oils). The main problem in the country is insufficient consumption of potatoes -18.5%, fruits-15.3%, milk-8%, eggs-2.7%, fish products-5.6% and other food products in the recommended norm.

It can be concluded that the diet of the country's population is insufficiently balanced in terms of basic and food products of particular importance for human life. As a confirmation of what has been said, we can consider the influence of income and solvency of the population, various social groups on the structure of the diet. Sharp differences in the income of the population by social groups are the main regulator of consumer demand, and also determine the direction and distribution of funds for food and other consumer goods.

In 2020, the population's expenditures on food according to the I quantile in the Republic of Azerbaijan amounted to 51.9% of the total number of consumer expenditures. In the III decile group of the population by income, this indicator was 42.5%, and in the V quantile with the highest incomes of the population – 31.4%.

Statistical materials on food products of various social groups show that over the past 10 years, the lower strata of the population have begun to eat better, which means that there has been a leap in the quality of life. But the diet of the rich is impoverished from the point of view of dietetics (figure 1).

Figure 1: The Level of Food Consumption in Azerbaijani Households in 2016-2020 (kg/person)

Source: the drawing was compiled by the author based on the source [10].

If we look not at the price, but at the structure of the food of the richest and the poorest, we will see that the difference is quite large, and it is not only the level of income that affects it. Part of the population with low incomes almost completely falls short of well-off families. For comparison, it should be said that if in 2000, representatives of the low-income group of the population consumed an average of 1,525 kcal per day, then this indicator in 2020 was 2,200 kcal.

The greatest difference in the consumption of lower-class foods was manifested in the consumption of proteins, vegetables, fruits and berries, which has significantly decreased over 10 years: but in 2020, according to its physiological parameters, the diet of this group corresponded to the norms of the World Health Organization.

For the market of agricultural food products, the problem of demand formation in the market under consideration is of particular importance. Its relevance can be justified by the fact that the supply and demand for food products have not been formed sufficiently due to low incomes of the population. However, it should be noted that in the 2015-2020s there were positive trends in the consumption of food by the population (see tab 2).

**Table 3: Food Consumption Per Capita by Income Quantiles in 2020
(In kilograms per year)**

	Income quantiles:				
	1	2	3	4	5
Bread and bakery products	132.2	134.5	135.6	135.9	137.6
Potato	72.5	72.6	73.1	73.1	74.5
Vegetable and melon products	104.2	106.2	108.9	109.7	113.9
Meat and meat products	32.6	33.4	33.8	34.1	35.2
Fish and fish products	6.9	7.1	7.3	7.4	7.9
Milk and dairy products	262.7	267.7	268.1	268.9	272.3
Egg, pcs.	158.0	159.0	160.0	161.0	165.0
Fruits, berries	76.4	77.8	79.3	80.0	81.9
Sugar and confectionery	29.4	29.9	30.3	30.4	31.5
Vegetable oil and margarine	10.3	10.5	10.7	10.8	11.3

Source: the table was compiled by the author based on the source [101].

Consumer demand and consumption of food products per capita depend on the ratio of income growth rates and the rate of change in prices for food products. Large and sharp differences between these two indicators create great risks and pose a serious threat to food security in the republic. As can be seen from table 3, real income growth increased across all sources in 2015-2020. Only in 2020, revenues decreased slightly due to the Covid-19 pandemic. It should be noted that there are some goods whose demand is growing despite the decline in real incomes. These goods are called “Giffen goods” or “inferior goods” [61]. If consumers' incomes increase, the demand for these products, on the contrary, decreases. As can be seen, demand and income fluctuate in different directions, while low-level goods are evaluated as goods with negative income elasticity.

**Table 4: Dynamics of Real Household Incomes in Azerbaijan Per Capita
(In manats) for 2015-2020**

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Income – in total	240.5	257.8	268.4	276.0	292.6	291.4
including						
Income received in connection with hired work	78.2	86.3	89.5	92.4	99.3	104.1
Income from entrepreneurship and self-employment	63.9	66.7	68.6	70.2	107.1	97.9
Income from agriculture	32.1	33.9	35.9	36.0	36.4	34.5
Rental income	1.7	1.8	1.8	1.9	2.5	1.7
Income from renting out real estate	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.6	1.9	1.2
Current transfers received	38.0	40.9	41.8	44.4	49.3	57.8
Pensions	32.2	34.7	35.9	37.7	41.4	48.3
Benefits and social assistance	3.9	4.1	5.1	6.0	7.5	9.2
The value of receipts in kind in monetary terms	2.0	2.0	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.3
Other income	26.0	27.8	30.2	30.6	34.4	29.9
Funds received from other families within the Country	19.7	21.1	23.1	23.5	27.1	24.1
Funds received from outside the country	6.3	6.7	7.1	7.1	7.3	5.8

Source: the table was compiled by the author based on the source [10].

During the period under review, there have been changes in the level of the population's demand for food (the ratio of actual consumption per capita to the norm of its rational consumption). Currently, Azerbaijan has a rational consumption rate approved by the Cabinet of Ministers. Table of standards for the consumption of basic foodstuffs (table.5).

Table 5: Consumption Rates of the Main Types of Food Products by the Minimum Consumer Basket (kg/Person Annually), in 2020

Products	Children	Able - bodied	Mature	On average, for each person of the entire population
Bread and bakery products (in flour equivalent)	100,5	136,8	107,9	126,2
Potato	42	54,8	40,2	50,7
Vegetable and melon products	100,7	97,2	85,2	97
Fruits and berries	76	38	32	46
Meat and meat products	29,6	32,9	25,6	31,5
Milk and dairy products (in milk equivalent)	258,6	223,6	233,8	232,3
Fish and fish products	8	7,7	6,8	7,7
Egg	183	150	100	153
Sugar and confectionery products (in sugar equivalent)	19,7	16,9	15,8	17,4
Vegetable oils, margarine and other fats	7	10,9	8,4	9,8
Butter	6	7	5,8	6,7

Source: the table was compiled by the author based on the source [13].

In the course of our research, we calculated the coefficient of availability of basic foodstuffs (Kn.p. = actual consumption/rational consumption rate per capita) and its dynamics in Azerbaijan in the 2010-2020s are reflected as follows.

This dynamic is based on fig.1. And tables 5 (Fig.2.).

Figure 2: Dynamics of the Demand Supply Coefficient in Azerbaijan

Source: it was compiled on the basis of Fig. 2. And Table 5

CONCLUSION

The change that occurs in food consumption with an increase in income can be divided into absolute and relative change. In absolute change they increase, in relative change they decrease (decrease). The relative decrease is manifested in a decrease in the amount of food costs in total costs. This is due to the fact that the elasticity of demand for food is decreasing, and the elasticity of savings for non-food products and funds is also decreasing.

Thus, as a result of our analysis, it became clear that if we look at the structure of food products of the upper and lower strata of the population of our country, we will see that the difference in consumption is quite large and it is influenced not only by the level of income. Part of the population with low incomes almost completely falls short of well-off families. For comparison, it should be said that if in 2000 representatives of the low-income group of the population consumed an average of 1,525 kcal per day, then in 2020 this figure was 2,200 kcal. The greatest difference in the consumption of lower-class foods was manifested in the consumption of proteins, vegetables, fruits and berries and has decreased significantly over the past 10 years. However, it should be noted that according to its physiological parameters in 2020, the diet of this group corresponded to the norms of the World Health Organization.

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